

Apparent energy of activation of BZ reaction with mixed organic substrate using different catalysts in a CSTR

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Abstract : Study of Belousov-Zhabotinsky reaction in a CSTR with oxalic acid and acetone as mixed organic substrate with Mn^{II} and Ce^{IV} as catalysts at different temperatures have been reported. The period and amplitude of oscillation of these oscillations have been recorded. Further the apparent energy of activation of these systems is calculated on the basis of monomolecular treatment taking the rate constant as inversely proportional to the time period of oscillation. The differences observed with these catalysts are compared and possible mechanistic implications are discussed.

Keywords : Energy of activation, catalysis, BZ-reaction.

The effect of temperature on oscillating chemical reactions has been studied earlier under batch conditions and the apparent energy of activation of systems composed of a variety of catalyzed and uncatalyzed bromate oscillators has been evaluated¹⁻¹⁰. Körös⁸ reported that the activation energy of the classical BZ oscillators was independent of the nature of the catalyst. Earlier Kulkarni *et al.*¹¹ reported the apparent energy of activation for the mixed organic substrate namely oxalic acid and acetone under batch conditions when Mn^{II} or Ce^{III} were the catalysts. Nagy *et al.*¹² have reported the dependence of the activation energy on the initial composition used. Recently as a preliminary experiment¹³ the temperature effect on Ce^{IV} catalyzed bromate system containing oxalic acid and acetone in a CSTR at a slightly high k_0 ($3.8 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1}$) and also at a lower $[BrO_3^-]_0$ (0.02 M) has been studied. Similar efforts are made here as a comparative study with different catalysts namely, Ce^{IV} and Mn^{II} at a lower value of k_0 and at a slightly increased $[BrO_3^-]_0$. The potential traces obtained at several temperatures are used for the calculation of apparent activation energy using Arrhenius equation and assuming the rate constant as inversely proportional to the time period. The slope of the plot of $\log(1/t)$ vs $1/T$ gives the apparent energy of activation.

Results and discussion

Tables 1 and 2 indicate the time periods of oscillations and the values of apparent energy of activation when Ce^{IV} and Mn^{II} are used as catalysts. It may be noted that

Table 1. Sulfuric acid- BrO_3^- -oxalic acid-acetone- Ce^{IV} system

Temp. (K)	$1/T \times 10^3$	Period (s)	$\log(1/t)$
293	3.41	225	-2.35
298	3.35	110	-2.04
303	3.30	80	-1.90
308	3.25	45	-1.65
313	3.20	25	-1.40
318	3.15	13	-1.11

$$E_a = 18.19 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$$

Composition : $[BrO_3^-]_0 = 0.03 M$, $[oxalic\ acid]_0 = 0.05 M$, $[H^+]_0 = 1.5 M$, $[acetone]_0 = 0.5 M$, $[Ce^{IV}]_0 = 0.001 M$ and $k_0 = 2.64 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1}$

Table 2. Sulfuric acid- BrO_3^- -oxalic acid-acetone- Mn^{II} system

Temp. (K)	$1/T \times 10^3$	Period (s)	$\log(1/t)$
293	3.41	190	-2.28
298	3.35	125	-2.10
303	3.30	80	-1.90
308	3.25	50	-1.70
313	3.20	35	-1.54
318	3.15	20	-1.30

$$E_a = 16.95 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$$

Composition : $[BrO_3^-]_0 = 0.03 M$, $[oxalic\ acid]_0 = 0.05 M$, $[H^+]_0 = 1.5 M$, $[acetone]_0 = 0.5 M$, $[Ce^{IV}]_0 = 0.001 M$ and $k_0 = 2.64 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1}$

under the indicated identical conditions the characteristic features of oscillations are similar. These oscillations show the hump at all the temperatures studied and the hump becomes sharper at higher temperatures. As regards the period of oscillations, the effect of temperature is similar to that observed earlier. Thus the period of oscillations decreases as the temperature is increased. Fig. 1 presents the plot of $\log(1/t)$ vs $(1/T)$ for both the Ce^{IV} and Mn^{II} systems.

Fig. 1. Arrhenius plot for apparent energy of activation : (●) Ce^{IV} catalyst, (▲) Mn^{II} catalyst.

The concept of apparent activation energy was initiated by Körös by making a gross simplification of a particular overall reaction in a single oscillation cycle. The process of oscillation in the mixed organic substrate reaction namely, oxalic acid and acetone involves the production of bromine due to the oxidation of oxalic acid by bromate and its consumption by bromination of acetone. The overall stoichiometry of the reaction may be written as⁹ :

where RH is acetone. However with the complex nature of oscillation it appears that the above stoichiometry could be time dependent and also dependent on the nature of metal catalyst used. Nagy *et al.*¹² have recently reported the values of apparent activation energy for various BZ systems both in batch and flow conditions. The varied values of apparent energy of activation obtained in their studies indicate that the situation is not simple. Actually the approach of Körös is based on a monomolecular treatment; the systems however, involve a number of steps. In all the above systems bromate and metal catalysts are common while the organic substrates are different. It may be possible that the autocatalytic bursts leading to the

production of bromine and oxidized metal species are similar but the later part of the period involving the consumption of bromine and the oxidized metal species are different. A better understanding could be possible if activation energies for various elementary steps were estimated on the lines of the work reported by Kumpinsky and Epstein¹⁴ for the minimal oscillator containing bromate-bromide- Mn^{II} in a CSTR.

Experimental

A schematic diagram of the CSTR experimental set up has been described in our earlier reports¹³. The parameters chosen are $[\text{BrO}_3^-]_0 = 0.03 \text{ M}$, $[\text{oxalic acid}]_0 = 0.05 \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}^+]_0 = 1.5 \text{ M}$, $[\text{acetone}]_0 = 0.5 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_0$ or $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]_0 = 0.001 \text{ M}$ and $k_0 = 2.64 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Temperature was varied from 293–318 K and the potential (using a bright Pt-electrode in the reaction mixture and a saturated calomel electrode as a reference electrode) were recorded for every 5 K.

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